

Modified paraffin method protocol for microtomy of delicate *Thismia* root specimens

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ABSTRACT

The conventional paraffin method is unsuitable for root specimens of *Thismia* (Thismiaceae), a genus of fully mycoheterotrophic plants, since it causes root tissues and associated fungal structures to become distorted or collapsed. Here, we present a modified paraffin method protocol optimized for vulnerable *Thismia* roots that mitigates this issue, with comparisons to the conventional method.

KEYWORDS: Fairy lantern, Mycoheterotrophy, Mycorrhiza, Plant anatomy, Sectioning, Thismiaceae

1. INTRODUCTION

Microtomy is a fundamental technique for studying anatomical features of organisms, including animals, plants¹, and fungi², as it allows observation of internal structures under a microscope. For plant materials, one of the most widely adopted procedures is the “paraffin method,” in which specimens are processed, infiltrated, and embedded in a suitable medium, typically a paraffin-plastic composite, and then sectioned into thin slices with a microtome for observation under a microscope^{3,4,5}.

Thismia Griff. (Thismiaceae J.Agardh), commonly known as “fairy lanterns,” is a genus of fully mycoheterotrophic achlorophyllous plants that are unable to photosynthesize and therefore rely on carbon obtained from fungi residing in their roots^{6,7}. Detailed examinations of root and fungal structures are crucial for understanding how anatomical and mycorrhizal symbiotic structures support their mycoheterotrophy⁸. However, when the conventional paraffin method^{3,4} is applied to their roots, their predominantly delicate tissues, including the epidermis, parenchyma, and associated fungal structures, often become severely distorted or collapsed after prolonged exposure to heat during the infiltration process. Here, we describe a modified paraffin method optimized for *Thismia* roots and compare its performance with the conventional approach.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Specimen selection

Roots of *Thismia* cf. *javanica* J.J.Sm., *Thismia mirabilis* K.Larsen and *T. thaithongiana* Chantanaorr. & Suddee were the representative materials for quality assessment of both conventional and modified methods. Since *Thismia* is rare^{6,8,9,10}, 2–4 roots per species were investigated. Feller et al. (2022)⁸ reported low intraspecific variation in root and associated mycorrhizal structures, suggesting that a small number of specimens is sufficient for method evaluation.

2.2 Protocol of the modified method

2.2.1 Specimen preparation, dehydration, and infiltration

After collection, roots of *Thismia* are cleaned with water to remove adhering dirt and fixed in 70% formalin-aceto-alcohol (FAA; 5:5:90 formaldehyde, glacial acetic acid, and 70% v/v ethanol). Before use, specimens are soaked in 70% v/v ethanol overnight, and this step is repeated at least once. Specimens are cut into approximately 1 × 1 cm pieces (Figure 1a) and dehydrated through a graded ethanol series¹¹ (70%, 80%, 95%, and absolute ethanol) for 20 minutes per solution (Figure 1b). No repetition is needed at each concentration.

The tissues are then infiltrated with 1:1 mixture of absolute ethanol and *tert*-butyl alcohol (TBA), absolute TBA (Figure 1b), and 1:1 mixture of TBA and paraffin oil in sequence (Figure 1c). Before each solution change preceding oven incubation, a vacuum pump is applied to remove air trapped within the specimens. It should be noted that pure TBA readily solidifies under reduced pressure. Thus, the vacuum should be applied with caution during the absolute TBA step.

Specimens are then incubated in a hot-air oven at 62 °C for 40 minutes, then transferred to paraffin oil. The paraffin oil is briefly heated over an alcohol burner until schlieren (optical inhomogeneities in transparent media) become visible (Figure 1d). The vials are returned to the oven and incubated for further 20 minutes (Figure 1e). The liquid is then rapidly decanted and replaced with a preheated appropriate molten paraffin-plastic composite. Leica Surgipath Paraplast (56 °C melting point) was utilized for demonstration in this protocol. The Paraplast is again briefly heated until schlieren are observed (Figure 1d), incubated at 62 °C for 30 minutes (Figure 1e), and this Paraplast infiltration step is repeated once.

2.2.2 Embedding

Metal molds are filled with molten Paraplast and the specimens are transferred into the molds. Only one root segment should be placed in each mold. Specimen position is adjusted using heated forceps when the Paraplast at the bottom of the mold begins to solidify (Figure 1f). Immediately after the surface of the Paraplast starts to solidify, an embedding ring is placed on the mold and additional molten Paraplast is added into the ring until full. Blocks are cooled at room temperature for at least 20 minutes and then frozen until microtomy.

2.2.3 Microtomy

Paraffin blocks are sectioned to ribbons using a rotary microtome (Leica RM2125) at an ambient temperature below 25 °C (Figure 1g). Before cutting each ribbon, ice or cooling gel is briefly applied to the block surface. Sections of 7 μm are made, and ribbons are floated on water at 42–45 °C before being mounted onto microscope slides pre-coated with Haupt's gelatin adhesive (Figure 1h). After that, slides are dried at room temperature.

2.2.4 Staining, deparaffinization, and permanently mounting

Sections are stained with 0.1% m/v toluidine blue O in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.0) for 10–25 minutes. Excess stain is removed by distilled water, and the slides are dried at room temperature. Sections are deparaffinized by immersion in xylene for 5 minutes and then cleared in two changes of pure xylene (5 minutes each) (Figure 1i). They are permanently mounted with a coverslip using a mounting medium (Coverquick 2000, Q Path®) (Figure 1j). Approximately 15 minutes after mounting, a small metal weight is placed on the coverslip to expel trapped air and excess mounting medium, and the slides are left to dry completely before observation under a light microscope.

Figure 1 Steps of the modified paraffin method for *Thismia* roots. (a) Cutting the specimen into approximately 1 × 1 cm pieces. (b) Dehydration with a graded ethanol series and infiltration with *tert*-butyl alcohol. (c–e) Infiltration: (c) with 1:1 *tert*-butyl alcohol and paraffin oil; (d) with paraffin oil and molten embedding material, respectively, heated using an alcohol burner; (e) with paraffin oil and molten embedding material, respectively, in a hot-air oven. (f) Embedding. (g) Microtomy. (h) Floating ribbons on a water bath. (i) Staining and deparaffinization in Coplin jars. (j) Mounting. Subfigures a–e, and j were created using Canva. Subfigures f–i were generated using Nano Banana and Nano Banana Pro AI models.

2.3 Specimen processing using the conventional method

For the conventional method, the specimens were mainly prepared following Johansen (1940)³ and Kermanee (2008)⁴. However, we made minor modifications. Root specimens were dehydrated through an ascending ethanol series¹¹. Then, specimens were embedded in metal molds and covered with embedding rings. A step-by-step comparison of both workflows is provided in Table 1.

2.4 Method evaluation

Scoring¹² for each method was based on three aspects: cell wall integrity, fungal visibility, and tissue continuity. We used a three-point ordinal scale, where 1 indicates the best and 3 indicates the worst. Six micrographs (Figure 2) selected from sections of three *Thismia* spp. were scored by the same evaluators (n = 3) using the predefined criteria (Table 2).

Table 1 Step-by-step comparisons between the conventional and the modified method

Step	The conventional method ^{3,4}	The modified method
Preparation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rinse specimens with water to remove dirt. • Fix specimens with 70% FAA. • Wash specimens with 70% v/v ethanol to remove fixative. • Cut specimens into approximately 1 × 1 cm pieces. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rinse specimens with water to remove dirt. • Fix specimens with 70% FAA. • Wash specimens with 70% v/v ethanol to remove fixative. • Cut specimens into approximately 1 × 1 cm pieces.

Step	The conventional method ^{3,4}	The modified method
Dehydration	A graded ethanol series is used. In each concentration, specimens are soaked twice, for 24 hours per soak.	A graded ethanol series is used. In each concentration, specimens are soaked once, for 20 minutes.
Infiltration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soak specimens in 1:1 absolute ethanol and TBA, and pure TBA, respectively. In each solution, soak twice for 24 hours per soak. • Replace with 1:1 TBA and paraffin oil and heat in a hot-air oven at 62 °C for 12 hours. Repeat twice. • Replace with paraffin oil and heat in a hot-air oven for 12 hours. • Replace with molten Paraplast and heat in a hot-air oven for 12 hours. Repeat twice. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soak specimens in 1:1 absolute ethanol and TBA, and pure TBA, respectively. In each solution, soak once for 20 minutes. • Replace with 1:1 TBA and paraffin oil and heat in a hot-air oven at 62 °C for 40 minutes. • Replace with paraffin oil, briefly heat over a flame, and heat in a hot-air oven for 20 minutes. • Replace with Paraplast, briefly heat over a flame, and heat in a hot-air oven for 30 minutes. Repeat once.
Embedding	Embed specimens within molten Paraplast using metal molds and embedding rings.	Embed specimens within molten Paraplast using metal molds and embedding rings.
Microtomy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Section specimens using a rotary microtome. • Float ribbons on 42–45 °C water, then mount them on microscope slides pre-coated with Haupt's gelatin adhesive. • Air-dry at room temperature. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Section specimens using a rotary microtome. • Float ribbons on 42–45 °C water, then mount them on microscope slides pre-coated with Haupt's gelatin adhesive. • Air-dry at room temperature.
Staining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stain sections in 0.1% m/v toluidine blue O in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.0) for 10–25 minutes. • Briefly rinse in water to remove excess stain. • Air-dry at room temperature. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stain sections in 0.1% m/v toluidine blue O in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.0) for 10–25 minutes. • Briefly rinse in water to remove excess stain. • Air-dry at room temperature.
Deparaffinization & permanently mounting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immerse slides in xylene sequentially for 5, 15, and 15 minutes. • Mount a coverslip using an appropriate mounting medium. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immerse slides in xylene sequentially for 5, 15, and 15 minutes. • Mount a coverslip using an appropriate mounting medium. • Place a metal weight on the coverslip to expel excess mounting medium and remove trapped air bubbles.

Figure 2 Sections of *Thismia* spp. roots prepared by two distinct paraffin methods. (a–b) Sections of *T. thaithongiana* roots: (a) conventional method; (b) modified method. (c–d) Sections of *T. cf. javanica* roots: (c) conventional method; (d) modified method. (e–f) Sections of *T. mirabilis* roots: (e) conventional method; (f) modified method. Abbreviations: c = cortex, e = epidermis, h = hypha, r = raphide, v = fungal vesicle, vc = vascular cylinder. Photographed at 5× magnification by J. Sangrattanaprasert.

Table 2 Criteria and scoring system for method evaluation

Criterion	Score		
	1	2	3
Cell wall integrity	>70% of cell walls are intact with no obvious distortion or collapse. Large cellular contents are clearly visible.	50–70% of cell walls are intact. The remaining cells show mild to moderate distortion or collapse. Large cellular contents are partially visible.	<50% of cell walls are intact. Distortion or collapse is widespread. Large cellular contents are poorly visible.
Fungal visibility	Most to all fungal structures are sufficiently visible to distinguish differences within each cell.	Fungal structures are moderately visible, allowing partial distinction of differences within each cell.	Fungal structures are not clearly visible, making it difficult to distinguish differences within each cell.
Tissue continuity	>70% of the tissue is continuous, with minimal tearing or separation.	50–70% of the tissue is continuous, with moderate tearing or separation.	<50% of the tissue is continuous, with extensive tearing or separation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results

In specimens processed with the conventional paraffin method, the epidermis and parenchyma appeared collapsed, with irregular cell shapes and indistinct cell walls (Figure 2a, c, e). This distortion made it moderately difficult to distinguish the boundaries between the plant cells and the intracellular fungal structures. On the other hand, the modified protocol resulted in excellent preservation of cellular structures. The epidermal and cortical cells of *Thismia* retained their turgidity and original shape (Figure 2b, d, f). Crucially, the cytoplasm was not retracted from the cell walls, allowing for a clear delineation of the cell lumen. This preservation extends to the associated fungal structures; the distinct morphology of fungal materials within the epidermal and cortical cells was clearly observable, permitting detailed study of the mycorrhizal interface.

Regarding tissue continuity, sections prepared using the conventional method showed frequent tearing and tissue separation in some regions, which limited observation of root anatomy and associated fungal structures. In contrast, sections prepared using the modified method remained largely intact, allowing more continuous visualization of both root tissues and fungal features (Figure 2). The ordinal scores for each criterion are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3 Method evaluation results

Method	Aspect	Proportion of each score			Mode
		1	2	3	
The conventional method ^{3,4}	Cell wall integrity	0.00	0.22	0.78	3
	Fungal visibility	0.00	0.56	0.44	2
	Tissue continuity	0.00	0.67	0.33	2
The modified method	Cell wall integrity	0.67	0.33	0.00	1
	Fungal visibility	0.56	0.44	0.00	1
	Tissue continuity	0.67	0.22	0.11	1

3.2 Discussion

Comparison of the sections showed a marked difference in cell wall integrity and a smaller difference in fungal visibility between the two protocols. As the protocols differed mainly in dehydration duration and the time spent under heat during infiltration, prolonged heat exposure is a plausible primary cause of the distortion and collapse observed with the conventional method. Since the specimens were fixed and stored in 70% FAA, which contains ethanol, extended exposure to alcohol during dehydration is less likely to be the main cause of damage. Therefore, the conventional method may be more suitable for tissues with robust, secondary-walled cells, such as *Balanophora*¹³ and *Paphiopedilum*¹⁴, where longer heating can help achieve complete Paraplast infiltration.

For the *Thismia thaithongiana* root processed using the conventional method, the large tear observed in Figure 2a may have resulted from tearing during flotation.¹⁵ A locally fragile region can tear repeatedly at a similar position as successive sections are floated, producing a recurring defect across multiple sections. This issue could bias the interpretation of the method evaluation.

In our slight modification of the conventional method, root specimens were dehydrated using a graded ethanol series¹¹ rather than a TBA series^{3,4}, as ethanol is less costly and reduces exposure time to volatile TBA.

4. CONCLUSION

The success of this modified protocol can be attributed to addressing the specific nature of *Thismia* roots. As fully mycoheterotrophic plants, they rely on fungi for carbon and lack the extensive structural support tissues often found in autotrophic plants. These delicate tissues are therefore more prone to distortion and collapse during the conventional paraffin method. By better accommodating this tissue vulnerability, the modified protocol preserves tissue integrity more effectively, enabling clearer observation of both root anatomy and associated mycorrhizal structures.

5. AUTHOR INFORMATION

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Author Contributions

The protocol was developed by both authors. T.A. drafted the manuscript. J.S. reviewed the manuscript.

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